

Aberrant sialylation in colorectal cancer and novel platform for Glycomic Data Visualization

Rita Adubeiro Lourenço^{1,2}, Daniela Pinto^{1,2}, Daniela Barreira^{1,2,3}, Marta Martins⁴, Raquel Cruz Duarte⁴, Sandra Casimiro⁴, Paula Borralho⁴, Luís Costa^{4,5}, Oleg Mayboroda⁶, Noortje De Haan⁶, Manfred Wuhrer⁶, Ana Rita Grosso^{1,2}, Paula Videira^{1,2,3}

¹ *i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Largo da Torre, 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

² *Departamento Ciências da Vida, UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

³ *CDG & Allies – Professionals and Patient Associations International Network (CDG & Allies – PPAIN), 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

⁴ *Instituto de Medicina Molecular-João Lobo Antunes, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, 1649-028 Lisbon, Portugal.*

⁵ *Oncology Division, Hospital de Santa Maria, Centro Hospitalar Lisboa Norte, 1649-028 Lisbon, Portugal.*

⁶ *Center for Proteomics and Metabolomics, Leiden University Medical Center, Netherlands.*

p.videira@fct.unl.pt

Aberrant sialylation patterns, characterized by the elevated presence of atypical sialylated glycans such as the cancer-associated antigen sialyl-Tn (STn), are commonly observed in cancer cells. STn's occurrence on cell surface glycoproteins generally correlates with poor prognosis and an immunosuppressive microenvironment, highlighting its potential as a diagnostic biomarker and therapeutic target in cancer research and treatment. This study explores the clinical and biological relevance of STn in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) and colorectal cancer (CRC). By applying immunohistochemistry to tumour tissue samples from patients, we aim to correlate STn expression with clinical outcomes and gain deeper insights into the role of this truncated O-glycan. Using transcriptomic data from CRC tumour tissues and immunohistochemistry staining for the STn, we were able to establish a correlation between STn expression and the *ST6GALNAC1* gene, alongside other genes important for glycosylation processes. Additionally, exploiting the cancer transcriptome available from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) for both CRC and TNBC, we employed the *ST6GALNAC1* gene expression to explore this biomarker at the gene level. Our findings revealed reduced overall survival associated with STn expression in the TNBC tissue cohort and increased cell proliferation in the TNBC MDA-MB-231 cell line overexpressing the STn antigen. Moreover, we identified a significant negative correlation with c-Myc, potentially explained by the significant positive correlation with genes involved in the TGF- β pathway. Additionally, a substantial proportion of gene signatures associated *ST6GALNAC1* gene expression with immune regulation genes. Subsequent analysis unveiled a positive correlation between *ST6GALNAC1* expression and the presence of immune cell infiltrates, particularly macrophage M2 and regulatory T

cells, suggesting potential immunosuppressive regulatory mechanisms shaping the tumour microenvironment. These analyses provide comprehensive insights into the impact of *ST6GALNAC1* expression on biological processes and immune cell infiltration, thereby enhancing our understanding of cancer pathology. Additionally, the use of cell lines expressing STn or other pertinent O-glycans presents an opportunity for in vitro validation of our findings. In support of this, a platform for the interactive visualization of cancer cell line glycomes is currently being developed through the GLYCOTwinning project.

References

1. Carrascal MA, Severino PF, Guadalupe Cabral M, Silva M, Ferreira JA, Calais F, Quinto H, Pen C, Ligeiro D, Santos LL, Dall'Olio F, Videira PA. Sialyl Tn-expressing bladder cancer cells induce a tolerogenic phenotype in innate and adaptive immune cells. *Mol Oncol*. 2014 May;8(3):753-65. doi: 10.1016/j.molonc.2014.02.008. Epub 2014 Mar 6. PMID: 24656965; PMCID: PMC5528624.

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